

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer Review Report For:

Loviscek, V. (2025). The role of powerful stakeholders towards responsible economy. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(1), e2024-0293. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250107>

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Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

Patricia Guarnieri , Universidade de Brasília, Departamento de Administração, Brasília, DF, Brazil. The other reviewers did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 2 Report

Reviewer: Patricia Guarnieri

Date review returned: 01-Jul-2024

Recommendation: Major revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

No conflicts of interest

Comments to the Author:

This paper intends to analyse the stakeholders of the Built Environment (BE) of the public sector, private sector and third sector to understand if and how “powerful” stakeholders are driving responsible actions. Despite it presents a relevant and interesting idea, it is necessary to improve some aspects of the paper.

Introduction

Please detail the acronyms when you cite it for the first time, for example, UKGBC

I was confused by the text: “The gap of knowledge among stakeholders has been observed.” Where was it observed? Is it part of the results of the study? Or derived from literature observation?

At the end of the Introduction, the authors state: “case study of the municipalities of London and São Paulo, focusing on the “meso level” of the Built Environment

and analysing the life cycle of buildings.”

I did not understand why the study refers to the meso level and not macro level, in the study:

Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. Resources, conservation and recycling, 127, 221-232.

It is clear that the study of countries, regions and cities is in the macro level of Analysis; the meso level would cover the study of industrial symbiosis and agglomerations of companies. Please explain better why you considered the meso level.

You did not explain how the stakeholder theory is related with your study. Please discuss it better in the Introduction.

I did not find the discussion of the research gap in the introduction, the research question, or the objective of the paper. These elements are necessary to point out how your study differentiates from those already published; besides that, it would prove the relevance and novelty of your study.

To finalize the Introduction it is important to highlight the contributions of the paper.

The Introduction should contain all the elements of the paper in order to attract the readers.

Theoretical underpinnings

I missed a review of the state-of-the-art related to the circular economy and the built environment. We need to understand what was already published and how your study differentiates from these studies.

Methodology

Please correct: the methodology is written with an “h” between the “t” and “o”. Besides that, it is not adequate to use the word methodology to express the methods and procedures used to apply the research because this word represents the Science studying the methods. I recommend using Methodological procedures or Methodological steps.

It is necessary to classify the research as applied/basic, exploratory/descriptive/explicative, qualitative or quantitative, and regarding the Technical procedure or strategy.

How the script for semi-structured interviews was elaborated? It was based on a validated instrument? It was validated by experts? Please present a list of questions used in the script.

How the interviewees were accessed?

Discussion:

I missed an in-depth discussion related to stakeholder theory and your findings.

Results:

It would be great to have some tables or figures in the results summarizing the main findings.

Conclusion

I missed the main contributions of the study (theoretical, methodological, practical, social). How your study is important to an international audience? How does your study advance in the state of knowledge?

What are the limitations of your study and the suggestions for further studies?

Finally, the paper needs to be edited by a copyeditor for English.

Authors' Responses

Dear Editors,

I am writing to express my sincere gratitude for the opportunity to revise my manuscript titled “THE ROLE OF POWERFUL STAKEHOLDERS TOWARDS RESPONSIBLE ECONOMY”.

I appreciate the thorough and insightful feedback provided by the reviewers. Their expertise has been invaluable in enhancing the quality of my work.

In response to the reviewers' comments, I have made significant revisions to the manuscript, which include:

- Clarifying sections of the theoretical foundation and analysis to enhance clarity and coherence.
- Improving the presentation and interpretation of the data to facilitate better understanding.
- Refining the discussion of the results to highlight their applicability and relevance more effectively.

I believe these revisions have substantially improved the manuscript, and I hope it now meets the standards for publication in RAE. To assist in the review process, I have included a detailed, point-by-point response to each of the reviewers' comments below.

Detailed Responses to Reviewers' Comments

Comment Reviewer 1: “1) The introductory/opening section should communicate a little clearer the literature gaps, as well as the study's aims & objectives in order to facilitate the flow of the study.”

Answer: Thank you for your insightful comment. Your direction has helped me structured the introduction in a more appropriate way.

I have revised the introductory section to more clearly communicate the literature gaps and the study's aims and objectives. Specifically, I have expanded the introduction to include discussions on the critiques and limitations of the circular economy, referencing Corvellec et al. (2022) and Zink & Geyer (2017) to highlight the need for a nuanced approach. Additionally, I have emphasized the lack of clarity regarding the practical

implementation of circular economy principles in the built environment, as discussed by Geisendorf & Pietrulla (2018).

I have clarified the study's aim to analyse the roles of powerful stakeholders in driving responsible actions within the built environment. The introduction now explicitly outlines the focus on stakeholders in the public, private, and third sectors, and their influence on implementing circular economy practices. I have also highlighted our comparative case study approach between London (UK) and São Paulo (Brazil) to provide context for the study's objectives.

Comment Reviewer 1: “2) Overall there are good arguments and well researched points made in this paper, but I feel that author needs to take to a further level. I recommend that you include the following references focused on the topic:

Corvellec, H., Stowell, A. F., & Johansson, N. (2022).

Geisendorf, S., & Pietrulla, F. (2018).

Han Y.; Xie L. (2023).

Höpfl F.; Peisl T.; Greiner C. (2023).

Skare M.; Gavurova B.; Kovac V. (2023). I

Wang Z.-J.; Chen Z.-S.; Xiao L.; Su Q.; Govindan K.; Skibniewski M.J. (2023).

Zhao Y.; Wen S.; Zhou T.; Liu W.; Yu H.; Xu H. (2022).

Zheng Y.; Liu S.; Zhao Y.; Han C.; Zhou Q.; Wang L.; Colace F.; Alhalabi W.; Alsharif H. (2023).

Zhu X.-X.; Mu Q.-R.; Liang W.-Z. (2022).

Zink, T., & Geyer, R. (2017).

Answer: Thank you for your valuable feedback and for suggesting additional references. I appreciate your recognition of the well-researched points made in the paper and your suggestion to take the discussion to a further level. I have included the recommended references to strengthen the arguments and provide a more comprehensive view of the topic. The following references have been integrated into the paper to enhance the discussion and address the literature gap more effectively:

Corvellec, H., Stowell, A. F., & Johansson, N. (2022). This reference has been added to provide a critique of the circular economy, highlighting its limitations and potential rebound effects, which is crucial for a nuanced discussion.

Geisendorf, S., & Pietrulla, F. (2018). This study offers a detailed analysis and redefinition of circular economic concepts, contributing to a clearer understanding of practical implementation across different sectors.

Han, Y., & Xie, L. (2023). Leveraging platform network ties and stakeholder perspectives for sustainable solutions enhances the discussion on stakeholder collaboration and innovation.

Höpfl, F., Peisl, T., & Greiner, C. (2023). This reference supports the role of network ties in circular economy innovation, adding depth to the analysis of stakeholder interactions.

Wang, Z.-J., Chen, Z.-S., Xiao, L., Su, Q., Govindan, K., & Skibniewski, M.J. (2023). This reference is crucial for discussing digital transformation and sustainability in the construction industry, which aligns with the technological aspects of the circular economy.

Zhao, Y., Wen, S., Zhou, T., Liu, W., Yu, H., & Xu, H. (2022). The integration of big data analytics for circular economy in the built environment adds a technological perspective to the discussion.

Zink, T., & Geyer, R. (2017). This reference highlights the challenges and opportunities in the circular economy, providing a balanced view of the potential and limitations of circular practices.

These references have been integrated into the appropriate sections of the paper, ensuring that the discussion is enriched, and the arguments are well-supported by the latest research in the field. Thank you again for your constructive feedback and for guiding me towards these valuable resources.

Comment Reviewer 1: “3) The research is well-developed.”

Answer: Thank you for your positive feedback. I truly appreciate your recognition of the thorough development of our research.

Comment Reviewer 1: “4) At the end of the, the author should include clear statements as to where research should now go.”

Answer: Thank you for your valuable feedback. In response to your suggestion, I have added clear statements to the conclusion section of the paper regarding the future direction of research. The revised conclusion now includes the following statements:

“While this study provides significant insights, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations. The findings are based on specific contexts and may not be universally applicable. Future research should consider expanding the scope to include more diverse settings and stakeholder groups. Additionally, quantitative approaches could complement the qualitative findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of stakeholder dynamics.”

This addition aims to address the need for further research and outlines potential areas for future studies to build upon the findings of this paper.

Comment Reviewer 1: “5) Carefully check the references, so as to make sure they are all complete and follow the Guidelines to Authors.”

Answer: Thank you for your careful review and valuable feedback. I have meticulously reviewed and updated the references to ensure they are complete and adhere to the Guidelines to Authors. Each reference has been checked for accuracy and formatted according to the APA (7th edition) guidelines as specified.

All references cited within the text are now included in the References section, and any discrepancies have been corrected. Please find the updated and complete references list in the revised manuscript.

Comment Reviewer 1: “6) Finally, when you submit the corrected version, please do check thoroughly, in order to avoid grammar, syntax or structure/presentation flaws.”

Answer: Thank you for your valuable suggestion. I acknowledge the importance of ensuring the clarity and readability of the manuscript.

The manuscript has been professionally copyedited to enhance the quality of English. This includes correcting grammatical errors, improving sentence structure, and ensuring consistency in terminology and style. I believe these efforts have significantly improved the manuscript’s clarity and coherence. I appreciate your feedback and trust that the revised version meets the expected standards of linguistic quality.

Comment Reviewer 2: “Introduction Please detail the acronyms when you cite it for the first time, for example, UKGBC”

Answer: Thank you for your comment. I have revised the introduction to detail all acronyms when they are first mentioned, including UKGBC (UK Green Building Council). This will enhance clarity for the readers.

Comment Reviewer 2: “I was confused by the text: “The gap of knowledge among stakeholders has been observed.” Where was it observed? Is it part of the results of the study? Or derived from literature observation?”

Answer: Thank you for your comment. The statement “The gap of knowledge among stakeholders has been observed” was derived from literature observation and not from the results of the study.

I have revised the introduction to clarify this, citing specific literature sources such as Benachio et al. (2020), Bertassini et al. (2021), and Arup (2016) to support the observation of these knowledge gaps among stakeholders. This should eliminate any confusion regarding the origin of this statement and provide clear attribution to existing literature.

Comment Reviewer 2: “At the end of the Introduction, the authors state: “case study of the municipalities of London and São Paulo, focusing on the “meso level” of the Built Environment and analysing the life cycle of buildings.” I did not understand why the study refers to the meso level and not macro level, in the study: Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, conservation and recycling*, 127, 221-232.

It is clear that the study of countries, regions and cities is in the macro level of Analysis; the meso level would cover the study of industrial symbiosis and agglomerations of companies. Please explain better why you considered the meso level.”

Answer: Thank you for your valuable comment. I acknowledge the need to clarify our use of the term “meso level” in the context of our study. In the study by Kirchherr et al. (2017), the macro level refers to the study of countries, regions, and cities. However, our research focuses on the built environment at the scale of individual buildings within the municipalities of London and São Paulo.

I use the term “meso level” to describe our analysis because I am examining the life cycle of buildings, including their construction, use, and end-of-life stages. This focus allows me to provide detailed insights into how circular economy practices are implemented within specific structures. By concentrating on individual buildings rather than broader regional or city-wide policies, it was possible to explore more deeply the interactions and responsibilities of stakeholders at this level.

To avoid confusion, I have revised the introduction to explicitly define the use of “meso level” and clarify that our study is centered on the detailed analysis of individual buildings within the municipalities, rather than the cities as a whole. I hope this explanation resolves any confusion regarding our use of the term and aligns with the scope of our research.

Comment Reviewer 2: “You did not explain how the stakeholder theory is related with your study. Please discuss it better in the Introduction.”

Answer: Your comment is very pertinent for this section. I have revised the introduction to better explain how stakeholder theory is related to our study. Specifically, I have integrated a discussion of stakeholder theory to clarify its relevance and application in our research.

“Stakeholder theory provides a useful framework for understanding the interactions and influence of different

stakeholders in this context. According to stakeholder theory, stakeholders hold varying levels of power, legitimacy, and urgency, which influence their ability to affect organizational decisions and outcomes (Mitchell et al., 1997). In the built environment, stakeholders such as government bodies, private companies, and NGOs play crucial roles in driving the adoption of circular economy practices. By examining these interactions, we can better understand how powerful stakeholders can lead the transition towards a sustainable and responsible economy.”

Comment Reviewer 2: “I did not find the discussion of the research gap in the introduction, the research question, or the objective of the paper. These elements are necessary to point out how your study differentiates from those already published; besides that, it would prove the relevance and novelty of your study.”

Answer: Thank you for your feedback. I have revised the introduction to clearly discuss the research gap, the research question, and the objective of the paper. The revised introduction now points out how our study differentiates from existing literature and emphasizes its relevance and novelty.

Specifically, I have pointed out the research gaps related to “specific roles and influences of powerful stakeholders in the built environment, particularly at the level of individual buildings”.

The last three paragraphs of the introduction are specifically related to the gap and the objective of the research. I hope this structure provides the details to differentiate the novelty of this study.

Comment Reviewer 2: “To finalize the Introduction it is important to highlight the contributions of the paper. The Introduction should contain all the elements of the paper in order to attract the readers.”

Answer: Thank you for your suggestion. I have included a last paragraph in the introduction pointing out the main contributions of the paper.

“This paper makes several key contributions to the literature on circular economy and stakeholder theory. It identifies the specific roles and influences of powerful stakeholders in the implementation of circular economy practices, highlighting the importance of stakeholder collaboration and interaction (Mitchell et al., 1997; Kirchherr et al., 2017). Second, the comparative case study approach between London and São Paulo offers valuable lessons and strategies that can be applied in diverse urban contexts (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Pomponi & Moncaster, 2017). Finally, the study’s findings contribute to the development of targeted stakeholder strategies and interventions that can enhance the sustainability of the built environment at the meso level, making it a critical resource for policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers (Eikelenboom & de Jong, 2022; Velenturf & Purnell, 2021).”

Comment Reviewer 2: “Theoretical underpinnings I missed a review of the state-of-the-art related to the circular economy and the built environment. We need to understand what was already published and how your study differentiates from these studies.”

Answer: I agree with your comment. I have included a section related to this literature. This revised section now includes a state-of-the-art review, situating the current study within the broader context of existing literature.

“The current literature on circular economy (CE) in the built environment covers various levels of analysis and highlights numerous systemic challenges and potential solutions. Pomponi and Moncaster (2017) and Rios et al. (2022) explore the complexity and interdisciplinary nature of CE when applied at different scales, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach that addresses social, economic, and environmental issues simultaneously. Ghisellini et al. (2016) argue for the necessity of viewing CE as a complex system, requiring systemic solutions to address intertwined challenges.

Recent studies have also identified drivers and barriers to CE implementation in the built environment. Larsen et al. (2022) discuss the environmental imperatives that drive the adoption of CE principles, while Osei-Tutu et al. (2023) and Wuni (2022) highlight financial, economic, and regulatory barriers. Benachio et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of addressing information and knowledge gaps to facilitate CE adoption.

Despite significant research on the macro and micro levels, there is a recognized gap in meso-level studies focusing on individual buildings. Previous research, such as Geissdoerfer et al. (2017) and Lieder & Rashid (2016), calls for detailed investigations into how CE principles can be practically implemented at this scale. This study addresses this gap by examining the roles and influences of powerful stakeholders within the built environment at the meso level, particularly focusing on individual buildings.”

Comment Reviewer 2: “Methodology Please correct: the methodology is written with an “h” between the “t” and “o”. Besides that, it is not adequate to use the word methodology to express the methods and procedures used to apply the research because this word represents the Science studying the methods. I recommend using Methodological procedures or Methodological steps.”

Answer: I really appreciate your correction. I have modified the section title as suggested.

Comment Reviewer 2: “It is necessary to classify the research as applied/basic, exploratory/descriptive/explicative, qualitative or quantitative, and regarding the Technical procedure or strategy.”

Answer: I totally agree. I have included a paragraph with the required information.

“This research can be classified as applied and exploratory. It is applied because it seeks to generate practical solutions and insights for the implementation of circular economy practices in the built environment (Babbie, 2010). It is exploratory due to its aim to develop clear constructs, categories, or concepts that can be consequently tested in future research (Stebbins, 2001). The study employs a qualitative approach, focusing on understanding the complex dynamics and interactions between stakeholders in the built environment (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).”

Comment Reviewer 2: “How the script for semi-structured interviews was elaborated? It was based on a validated instrument? It was validated by experts? Please present a list of questions used in the script. How the interviewees were accessed?”

Answer: Thank you for your insightful comments. Here follows a detailed response to your queries. The responses below were added to the article to implement the clarification suggested.

How the script for semi-structured interviews was elaborated: “The script for the semi-structured interviews was developed based on an extensive literature review on circular economy practices and stakeholder theory, particularly focusing on the built environment. The literature review identified key themes and stakeholder attributes relevant to the study, which were used to formulate the interview questions.”

Validation of the instrument, list of questions (Table 1): “The interview script (Table 1) was validated through a two-step process. First, the initial set of questions was reviewed and refined by a panel of experts in sustainability, circular economy, and stakeholder management to ensure comprehensiveness and relevance. Second, a pilot test was conducted with a small sample of stakeholders to ensure the clarity and effectiveness of the questions. Feedback from the pilot test was used to make final adjustments to the script.”

Accessing interviewees: “Interviewees were accessed using a purposive sampling method, beginning with key public agencies and NGOs involved in circular economy initiatives. Snowball sampling was then employed, where initial interviewees recommended additional relevant stakeholders. This approach ensured a diverse and comprehensive sample of stakeholders with significant expertise and experience in the field.”

Comment Reviewer 2: “Discussion: I missed an in-depth discussion related to stakeholder theory and your findings.”

Answer: I appreciate the interest in an in-depth discussion. I have reformulated the discussion part to be more concise. Specifically I have directed the argument on the concepts of power, legitimacy, and urgency as outlined by Mitchell et al. (1997) to explain the dynamics between stakeholders in London and São Paulo. I have also included a diagram (Figure 1) to visually represent the discussion.

Comment Reviewer 2: “Results: It would be great to have some tables or figures in the results summarizing the main findings.”

Answer: Thank you for the great insight. It’s true. I have added a table summarizing key findings. I hope the table satisfies the standards expected by the journal. I also included a diagram (figure 1) in the Discussion displaying the main findings and relationships among stakeholders.

Comment Reviewer 2: “Conclusion. I missed the main contributions of the study (theoretical, methodological, practical, social). How your study is important to an international audience? How does your study advance in the state of knowledge? What are the limitations of your study and the suggestions for further studies?”

Answer: Thank you for your insightful comment. I have revised the conclusion to clearly outline the main contributions of the study and address its relevance to an international audience. Here are the key points included in the revised conclusion (last part of conclusion):

“ This study advances the state of knowledge by providing a detailed analysis of stakeholder interactions based on the attributes of power, legitimacy, and urgency. It enhances the understanding of how these attributes influence the implementation of circular economy practices in different contexts, particularly in the built environment of London and São Paulo.

The qualitative methodology employed in this research, including semi-structured interviews and document analysis, allowed for an in-depth exploration of stakeholder interactions and the identification of contextual characteristics. This approach provides a framework that can be replicated in similar contexts to understand stakeholder dynamics better.

Practically, the findings of this study offer actionable insights for organizations in the built environment sector. By understanding how different stakeholders interact and influence each other, organizations can develop more effective strategies to implement circular economy practices. This includes leveraging the power of influential stakeholders, fostering collaboration, and addressing knowledge gaps. Socially, this research underscores the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration in addressing sustainability challenges. By promoting circular economy principles, the study contributes to the broader goal of achieving sustainable development and reducing environmental impact, benefiting society as a whole.

This study’s comparative approach between London and São Paulo provides insights applicable to various global settings. By highlighting the similarities and differences in stakeholder interactions in developed and developing contexts, the research offers valuable lessons for international audiences aiming to promote circular economy practices.

While this study provides significant insights, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations. The findings are based on specific contexts and may not be universally applicable. Future research should consider expanding the scope to include more diverse settings and stakeholder groups. Additionally, quantitative approaches could complement the qualitative findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of stakeholder dynamics.”

Comment Reviewer 2: “Finally, the paper needs to be edited by a copyeditor for English.”

Answer: Thank you for your valuable suggestion. We acknowledge the importance of ensuring the clarity and readability of the manuscript. The manuscript has been professionally copyedited to enhance the quality of English. This includes correcting grammatical errors, improving sentence structure, and ensuring consistency in terminology and style.

I believe these efforts have significantly improved the manuscript’s clarity and coherence. I appreciate your feedback and trust that the revised version meets the expected standards of linguistic quality.

Once again, I extend my heartfelt thanks for the valuable contributions to this study.

Sincerely

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Patricia Guarnieri

Date review returned: 19-Aug-2024

Recommendation: Accept

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

No conflicts of interest

Comments to the Author

Dear authors,

Congrats for the work done. In my opinion, the paper is ready for publication after the corrections.

Reviewer 2 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.